

UZBEK CONJUGATION IN DIALECTS

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Annotation: The use of Uzbek conjugations in dialects and their differences in meaning. More than 10 variants of 6 consonants in dialects.

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As we know, words are pronounced differently in different regions. Not only words, but also affixes used in words (affix is the part of the word "attached" in Latin. a morpheme that serves to form or form a grammatical expression) is also pronounced in accordance with different regions. and most of them combine dialects with similar linguistic characteristics). The dialect characteristic of such regions (the Persian word "ravish", "style", "yosin" means means and in the science of dialectology, the branch of linguistics that studies the national, i.e., the part of the national language, which is distinguished by its own lexical-phonetic and grammatical features. Dialect is a word derived from the Greek word "dialect" and "speech" meaning logos-"doctrine". social appearance, accent. It is a dialect-Arabic word, which, like the word "dialect", means "manner", "style", "yousin", and as a dialectological term, it has long been characteristic of the development of the Uzbek language. refers to the largest group of dialects. In its historical development, the Uzbek language is composed of three dialects. They are the Qarluq-Chigil-Uighur dialect, the Kipchak dialect, and the Oghuz dialect.

Grammatical category is a general grammatical concept based on the rules of changing, combining and forming sentences with the help of special indicators. Grammatical categories are divided into morphological and syntactic categories according to which field of grammar they belong to. Syntactic categories are not equal to morphological categories. For example, our family is a family. Morphologically, this sentence has four words, three different word groups (pronoun, noun, adjective, and noun), and syntactically, it has only two parts and section is available. Affix (from Latin "attached") is the root of a word. It is a morpheme that opposes the root and serves to form a word or a grammatical expression. Accordingly, it is divided into two: word-former and form-former According to its position in relation to the stem, it comes at the beginning of the word (affix), in the middle of the word (infix), at the end of the word (suffix). olmazor), sometimes comes before the root (incorrectly, beish). It is known that during the initial development of the Turkish language, there were 7 forms of

conjugation, now the literary language of Uzbek is based on 6 forms of conjugation. In Uzbek dialects, this number can sometimes be reduced to four. Only Kipchak and northern Uzbek dialects - only 6 forms of agreement are fully preserved. In most dialects of the Oghuz dialect, it can also be expressed with 5 indicators in the dialects of Tashkent and Fergana. We can observe that the letter "y" is recorded in four ways in the dialects that use "j", that is, the nominative and accusative cases with the same indicators, and the destination and place-time agreement with the same indicator. is expressed. Let's get acquainted with the categories of such agreements. 1. Main agreement. There are no indicators in the main agreement. This agreement is without an indicator, and when analyzed syntactically, it easily fulfills the function of possessor.

2. Karatqich conjugation. Karatqich conjugation is mostly non-functional in most dialects of the Qarluq-Chigil-Uyghur dialect, in some dialects of the Oghuz dialect, that is, this category of conjugation is not used in dialects with four and five consonants. The following affixes are used in dialects with this agreement: -nin affix is added to words ending with many vowels and sonorous consonants: enangning-enenin-enanin, ota-otanin (Kipchak). The suffix -in is added to words ending with a consonant: kopinin toyi- kopinin toyi-kopinin toji, horse's head-atin bashi-atin basi (kipchak). The suffix -nun is added to words with a labial vowel and ending with a vowel or sonor: uning-onun, uying-uynun-ujnun (Kipchak) The -un affix is added to words that have a labial vowel and end with consonants: the pupil of the eye-the pupil of the eye-the pupil of the eye, the darkness of the night, sheep's wool-sheep's wool-sheep's wool. -din affix is added to words ending with a voiced consonant: biz-bizdin, their-olar-din-ulardin (Kipchak). -tin affix is added to words ending with voiced consonants: katakin-katextin-katakhtin, oting-ottin-attin (in Northern Uzbek dialects). The following affixes take part in the agreement of income: -n affix: get apple-almen be-almani almak (Tashkent dialect), sovni moq-suvn sepmak (in Northern Uzbek dialects). The -n variant is considered an archival variant and can be used in all dialects. The affix -i is added to words ending with a consonant, and is used in Karakol and Alot dialects: do the work-work-work-work-work, if you don't know the word, don't speak-if you don't know the word, don't speak-if you don't know the word, don't speak. The suffix --nu is added to words with a labial vowel in the last syllable. It is found in Karabulok and Mankent dialects: kozini-kozunu-kozinu, tulkini-tulkunu-tulkinu. All synharmonisms where the affix -di/ti is added to words ending in a consonant (Greek-syn "together" meaning

"harmony" and "harmony") are found in dialects with vowel harmony (harmony): mountain ni-tovdi-tavdi-togdi, yigitlarni-jigitlardi-zigitlardi-yigitardi, atni-atti-otti, menetkaslarni-meynatkaslarti-mijnatkashlarti-mijnatkaslarti. -di/ti variant is also used in groups of the Fergana region that use the Kipchak dialect: home-home, work-work- di-work. In most dialects, the consonant suffix -n refers to strong assimilation (assimilation-Latin assimilation means "to be similar" and the phenomenon of one of them becoming similar to another as a result of the impact of sounds on each other)) occurs. This is especially evident in the Tashkent dialect: kolni-koli, bashni-bashshi-bashshi. The unmarked use of the subjunctive is characteristic of all dialects: We came to see the bride-We came to see the bride-We came to see the bride, Even if the sparrow is killed, let the butcher kill it-Sparrow is slaughtered by the butcher-Sparrow is slaughtered by the butcher (Against). Agreement of dispatch. The following affixes are involved in the agreement of dispatch: -g'a/ka/qa affix. All variants of this affix are not used in synharmonic dialects. In dialects that have lost synharmonism, the variants -ge/ke are found: uyga-uyge-ujge, ishke-ishke-iske.-ka/ga ,-qa/g'a variant is added to bases with a back vowel in synharmonic dialects: oqishga-oqushga-oqushqa, dalaga-dalaga-dalaye. The affix -a can be found in the dialects of the Oghuz group and in the northern Uzbek dialects: koliga - kolima, gullarga - gullara. The affix -ya/ye/ja can be found in the Karshi dialect: khurmaga-khurmaya-khurmaja, iziga-uziya- oziya, It rained on the road while he was carrying yogurt to his older brother. kette ekesiye permede curd when it was raining. Affixes of the sending agreement also express the meaning of place in dialects with 4 agreements. This can be seen in the above examples of khurmaya-khurmaja, chekhga-chakhga, yolge-jolga. In the dialects of the Oguz dialect and the dialects of the Northern Uzbek, the personal pronouns in the case of departure are menga-mana, senge-sana, unga-una. In the dialects of the Kipchak dialect, magan-mayan, sagan-sayan, takes the form of ogan-oyan. Place-time agreement. Place-time agreement is accompanied by the affixes de/da, te/ta. Affixes -de/te, da/ta occur in all dialects, and affixes -da/ta, do/to occur in synharmonic dialects: work- ishe-ista, in-hand-in-hand-in-hand, in-in-in-in, meanwhile-in-the-middle-in-the-middle (kipchak) Exit agreement. 4 active affixes are involved in exit agreement: -den/dan/ten/tan affixes have a wide range of possible additions. These affixes can be used in all dialects: Bukharadan-Bukhoroden-Bukharaden, sendan-senden-sanden.

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